

**Projection spread caused by missingness
in PCA on modern African populations:
Approx. # non-missing SNPs = 60000**

**True position of individual
(Individual : Population)**

- BOT2.031 : Taa_West
- △ HGDP00920 : Yoruba
- + HG03100 : Esan
- × NAM321 : Nama
- ◇ BOT6.004 : Kgalagadi
- ▽ Ayodo_47K : Kikuyu
- ▣ Bar08 : Hadza1

Approx Geographical location a Central_Africa a East_Africa a South_Africa a West_Africa